

SZ-HB-II-02-02 Continuing to use a course from another LMS (English)

Author	@Ricarda Peil ; @Julia Lehmler ; @ Julia Victoria Dinier ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Sönke Erdmann (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15259918
ID	SZ-HB-II-02-02
Title	Continuing to use a course from another LMS
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Emil - Professor https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684426
Short description	Emil is moving his LMS courses from the University of Bonn to Humboldt University Berlin. He uses BIRD to facilitate the transfer, converting, editing, and temporarily saving the courses. He then transfers them to the HU Berlin's Moodle.
Result	Emil was able to convert his ILIAS courses into BIRD, adapt them, and transfer them to the Moodle platform of Humboldt University Berlin.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "Migration of a course between two different LMS"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emil is registered at BIRD• Emil is logged in to BIRD
Components	#workspace
Services / tools	#moodle #STUD-IP #serlo-editor

Problem scenario

Introduction

Emil Larssen works as a research assistant at the German Department of the University of Bonn. He has accepted a position as a visiting professor at the Humboldt University of Berlin and will be teaching there for a while. At his previous workplace, the University of Bonn, ILIAS is used as a learning management system (LMS). The HU Berlin, on the other hand, uses a Moodle system. So that Emil does not have to start completely over and can continue to use some of his old courses, he would like to “take” them with him to HU Berlin and use them at his new workplace.

Problem definition

Transferring his existing ILIAS courses, which include interactive content, quizzes, and wikis, to HU Moodle is a challenge for Emil. A regular ILIAS export cannot be imported into Moodle, so he cannot simply transfer the course structure or the built-in interactive content. Emil has invested a lot of time and effort into developing his ILIAS courses and would like to migrate them as unchanged as possible. Since he is moving to a different location and planning his seminars at the same time, Emil is looking for a simple and time-saving solution for the course move.

Background and context

It's very important to Emil to provide his students with high-quality, well-designed materials and course offerings. He knows that both the move and the adjustment period in a new city and university will require a lot of his attention. He is aware that, especially in the early stages, he will not be able to invest as much time in preparing new materials as he would like. It would therefore be very helpful for Emil to be able to transfer existing ILIAS courses quickly and easily and adapt them to the new environment.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Because Emil is very conscientious in his teaching and structured, high-quality courses meet his own standards, he feels stressed by the move to a new university. While he is looking forward to the new challenges and students in Berlin, he is also concerned that he might have difficulties getting started if he does not have access to the materials and courses in which he invested a lot of energy during his time at the University of Bonn. If he can't continue using the existing course materials, he would have to invest a lot of time and energy into creating new Moodle courses for his teaching at HU Berlin in order to maintain his own standards.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Emil contacted both the University Computer Center (HRZ) at the University of Bonn and the Computer and Media Service at HU Berlin to find out how he could export his courses from ILIAS to HU Moodle. There, however, he learned that a normal export would prevent him from reusing or continuing to use interactive content (H5P), quizzes, and the wiki. During a conversation with a colleague, Emil was informed that BIRD offers the option of connecting different LMSs via an LTI ([Learning Tools Interoperability](#)) interface, which allows content and activities to be seamlessly integrated.

Activity scenario

Process "Migration of a course between two different LMS"

Step 1: After talking with his colleague, Emil backs up his courses locally on his computer as a precaution and opens BIRD. Here he navigates to his personal workspace.

Step 2: First, Emil creates a new project within his workspace and calls it "Uni Courses".

Step 3: Using the tool selection, he adds the BIRD Moodle and ILIAS plugin to his project.

Step 4: Emil logs into ILIAS via SSO. Because the University of Bonn's ILIAS is connected to BIRD, he can select the option "Export course via LTI" in the course administration under the category "Export courses" and specify BIRD as the destination.

Step 5: Emil imports the relevant courses from the University of Bonn's ILIAS into the BIRD workspace via the interface.

Step 6: Emil uses the BIRD workspace as a temporary storage location to back up his courses from Bonn, as he currently does not have access to the HU Moodle.

Step 7: In the workspace, Emil can update his ILIAS courses and, if necessary, adjust the formatting or edit content. The courses are displayed in BIRD Moodle the same way they are in ILIAS, meaning interactive content remains available.

Step 8: Emil uses BIRD Moodle as a safe "playground" to explore the new LMS, Moodle. He works on the courses both on his work computer and on his tablet at home. With the connected Serlo Editor, he can also edit and adapt the H5P content.

Step 9: Emil checks the content one last time and finally saves the courses.

Step 10: After Emil's access to HU Moodle has been activated, he has the option to transfer his courses there. For this purpose, Emil again uses the LTI interface provided by BIRD.